

refluxed for 24 hours under nitrogen atmosphere. It was diluted with water, the alcohol removed on the water-bath, and acidified, when a gum separated which gradually crystallised out. It was twice crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 214-15°. When mixed with the unsaturated acid from cedrene, it melted at 167-73°. (Found: C, 61.88; H, 7.86. $C_{11}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 62.25; H, 7.60 per cent).

These experiments were carried out in the chemical laboratories of E.T.H., Zürich, Switzerland and the author places on record his grateful thanks to Prof. Plattner and to Dr. A. Fürst for their kind help and encouragement and also for the laboratory facilities. Thanks are also due to the University of Calcutta for the award of the Ghosh Travelling Fellowship in science.

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SESQUITERPENES AND RELATED SUBSTANCES. PART V. SYNTHESIS OF ISOMERIC METHYL_{iso}PROPYL_{cyclo}HEPTANONES*

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Synthesis of 2-methyl-5-isopropyl- and 2-isopropyl-5-methylcycloheptanones has been described. These ketones are expected to be of use in the synthesis of substituted azulenes.

For the synthesis of substituted azulenes, S-guaiazulene (I) and Se-guaiazulene (II), isolated from naturally occurring sesquiterpenes, the alkylated cycloheptanones constitute important intermediates. The distribution of alkyl residues in (I) and (II) has finally been confirmed by synthesis (Plattner *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 32, 2137; Pliva *et al.*, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Com.*, 1951, 16, 158).

In the structural framework of carvone (III) and menthone (IV), the methyl and isopropyl groups are properly distributed and these may serve as convenient starting materials to realise the synthesis of these important azulenes. By applying the usual ring-expansion methods to these ketones, seven-membered ring ketones have been synthesised, but the constitution of these ketones could not be definitely settled in view of the alternative structures, possible from theoretical considerations (cf. H.C. Neumann, Dissertation, E.T.H., Zürich, 1949). It has been thought desirable to devise other methods for the synthesis of the seven-membered ketones from carvone and menthone, which will leave no ambiguity so far as the constitution of the final products is concerned.

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Experiments initiated with a view to synthesising the ketone (V) were carried out with the keto-ester (VI: Simonsen *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 316), which constituted the major product in the condensation of ethyl oxalate and tetrahydrocarvone. This product can be isolated in a reproducible yield, but the yield of the keto-ester (VI) appears to depend considerably on the presence of the quantity of sodium ethoxide. If ethyl oxalate is used in excess to keep the concentration of free sodium ethoxide as low as possible, the yield of the keto-ester falls considerably and during alkaline hydrolysis, a considerable quantity of tetrahydrocarvone is recovered. Reduction of the keto-group in (VI) was attempted by refluxing for a prolonged period with amalgamated zinc in alcoholic solution, saturated with dry hydrogen chloride (Smith and Rouault, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 746) and the keto-ester was recovered unchanged. Similar failure was also met with in the Clemmensen reduction. Finally the keto-ester was reduced catalytically in acetic acid solution in presence of platinum oxide catalyst to furnish (VII). Replacement of the hydroxyl group with thionyl chloride and pyridine led to incomplete reaction. Next it was allowed to react with PCl_5 ; the chloro-ester (VIII) was isolated in a satisfactory yield and an undistillable residue remained in the flask. The chloro-ester (VIII) on boiling with zinc dust in acetic acid solution led to the formation of the expected ester (IX). This on hydrolysis afforded the free acid (X) in an excellent yield. The dicarboxylic acid was converted into thorium salt, which on dry distillation furnished the ketone (V) in a good yield. The ketone afforded a mixture of semicarbazones from which two fractions crystallised out. The melting points of the semicarbazones do not indicate their stereochemical homogeneity, although the ketones generated from these two types of semicarbazones have the same boiling point and refractive index but slightly different values of optical rotation. It is most likely due to the fact that the asymmetric centre carrying the methyl group undergoes partial racemisation during ketonisation as it is α -to the carbonyl group.

Regarding the nature of the undistillable viscous residue left in the flask after distillation of the chloro-ester (VIII), the following product (XI) appeared to constitute the major fraction quite in analogy with the action of PCl_5 on cyanohydrins (Downer and Hornung, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 505).

In support of the ether-linkage, it was found that on prolonged boiling with hydroiodic acid and red phosphorous it led to the same acid (X) in a very good yield. This was characterised by a *p*-bromophenacyl derivative having a different melting point. The dicarboxylic acid obtained in this manner furnished the same ketone (V) on thorium salt distillation and from which again the same mixture of semicarbazones was obtained.

Synthetic investigations have also been extended in an identical way to menthone, as indicated below, to realise the synthesis of (XVII).

(XVII)

The fission of the condensation product from menthone and ethyl oxalate in presence of two molecules of sodium ethoxide proceeds only with a comparatively poor yield. Some of the experimental conditions have been tried, but the optimum conditions still remain to be found out. The keto-ester (XII) was reduced to the hydroxy-ester (XIII) catalytically and the latter was again converted into the chloro-ester (XIV) along with a non-distillable residue. It was reduced in acetic acid solution with zinc dust to furnish (XV), which on hydrolysis afforded the dicarboxylic acid (XVI) in a very good yield. The non-distillable residue from the distillation of the chloro-ester (XIV) was refluxed with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus, resulting in the formation of the dicarboxylic acid (XVI). The acid was characterised by a well-defined *p*-bromophenacyl derivative. The acid was converted into the ketone (XVII) through dry distillation of the thorium salt. The ketone has a smell, strongly reminiscent of menthone.

With a view to realising the synthesis of a C_{15} -azulene, experiments have been successfully carried out with 2-methyl-5-isopropylcycloheptanone, and these results will be published in a future communication.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl 1-Hydroxy-6-methyl-3-isopropylsuberate (VII).—The keto-ester (VI: 800 mg.) was hydrogenated in acetic acid (5 c.c.) in presence of platinum oxide catalyst (30 mg.) and absorption of the calculated amount of hydrogen was complete in half-an-hour. On filtering off the catalyst, it was distilled as a colorless oil, b. p. $135^{\circ}/0.1$ mm. It showed no ferric chloride coloration. (Found: C, 63.76; H, 9.99. $C_{16}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 63.6; H, 9.9 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Methyl-6-chloro-3-isopropylsuberate (VIII).—When the above hydroxy-ester (3 g.) was treated with PCl_5 (2.2 g.) in the cold, an immediate reaction started and a little of the pentachloride remained in excess. It was allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 hours and finally decomposed with ice. It was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, and finally it was distilled, when the chloro-ester (2.6 g.) was obtained, b. p. $126-30^{\circ}/0.1$ mm. There was a residue in the flask. (Found: C, 59.85; H, 9.15. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4Cl$ requires C, 59.89; H, 9.11 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Methyl-4-isopropylsuberate (IX).—The above chloro-ester (5.5 g.) was refluxed for 12 hours with zinc dust (4 g.) in acetic acid (40 c.c.). The

solution was poured into water, extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed with sodium carbonate solution and finally distilled. It passed over at $115-16^{\circ}/0.08$ mm., yield 4 g. (Found: C, 67.09; H, 10.55. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 67.09; H, 10.56 per cent).

1-Methyl-4-isopropylsuberic Acid (X).—The above ester (38 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with a solution of KOH (38 g.) in methanol (200 c.c.) for 20 hours. The methanol was removed on the water-bath and the solution was diluted with water, and acidified. The viscous mass was taken up in ether and finally distilled, when it passed over at $178^{\circ}/0.1$ mm., yield 30 g. (Found: C, 62.55; H, 9.57. $C_{19}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 62.58; H, 9.63 per cent). The *p*-bromophenacyl derivative was prepared in the usual manner and after repeated crystallisation from alcohol melted at $77-79^{\circ}$; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 14^{\circ}.4$ ($c=15.3$ mg./c.c. in chloroform). (Found: C, 53.67; H, 5.16. $C_{28}H_{32}O_4Br_2$ requires C, 53.86; H, 5.17 per cent).

2-Methyl-5-isopropylcycloheptanone (V).—The dicarboxylic acid (10 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (25 c.c.) and neutralised with a 10% NaOH solution, and heated to 70° . Thorium nitrate (14 g.) was dissolved in water (100 c.c.) and heated to 80° . This was vigorously stirred and to this was added the hot solution of the sodium salt all at once. It was stirred for 15 minutes more and was filtered. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with hot water to remove completely any thorium nitrate adhering to the precipitate. Next it was dried in steam, powdered and taken in a flask for dry distillation. At first it was heated to 200° to remove last traces of moisture, and towards the end water-suction was applied. The temperature was gradually raised to 350° in 2 hours. Decomposition started at 275° and finally the temperature was raised to 400° in the course of 1 hour. The distillate (5.5 g.) was taken up in ether and washed with sodium carbonate solution. On distillation in vacuum, the fraction boiling at $105-108^{\circ}/12$ mm. was collected. This was treated with sodium acetate and semicarbazide hydrochloride in methanol, whereupon crystals separated, which on washing with petroleum ether melted at $130-35^{\circ}$. This on twice crystallisation from methanol melted at $136-38^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 63.99; H, 10.26; N, 18.84. $C_{12}H_{22}ON_2$ requires C, 63.96; H, 10.29; N, 18.65 per cent).

The semicarbazone was mixed with an equal quantity of oxalic acid in water and steam-distilled; the ketone was obtained as a pleasant smelling liquid. It was extracted with ether and distilled, when it passed over at $105-106^{\circ}/10$ mm., yield quantitative; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 38^{\circ}.8$ ($c=15$ mg./c.c. in alcohol); d_4^{25} , 0.9268; n_D^{20} , 1.4660. (Found: C, 77.94; H, 12.07. $C_{11}H_{20}O$ requires C, 78.51; H, 11.98 per cent).

The above semicarbazone on repeated crystallisations from methyl alcohol yielded a small amount of the semicarbazone of m. p. 149-51 (Found: C, 63.95; H, 10.24; N, 18.61. $C_{12}H_{22}ON_2$ requires C, 63.96; H, 10.29; N, 18.65 per cent).

The ketone was regenerated from the semicarbazone in the usual way and distilled at $105-106^{\circ}/10$ mm. $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 41^{\circ}$ ($c=15$ mg./c.c. in alcohol); d_4^{25} , 0.9270. n_D^{20} , 1.4658. (Found: C, 78.22; H, 11.88. $C_{11}H_{20}O$ requires C, 78.51; H, 11.98 per cent).

The non-distillable residue (10 g.) from PCl_5 treatment of the hydroxy-ester, described before, was refluxed for 24 hours with HI (d 1.7; 50 g.) and red phosphorus (10 g.). In the beginning there was too much frothing and the condenser had to be removed sometimes to distill away EtI formed in the reaction. The mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. From the ethereal extract, the acid was washed down with sodium carbonate solution and regenerated on reacidification. The acid (4 g.) passed over at $180^\circ/0.1$ mm. (Found: C, 62.36; H, 9.75. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 62.58; H, 9.63 per cent).

The *p*-bromophenacyl derivative, prepared in the usual way, melted at 66-68 on twice crystallisation from alcohol. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $-1^\circ.3$ ($c=11.4$ mg./c.c. in chloroform). (Found: C, 53.99; H, 5.27. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_6\text{Br}_2$ requires C, 53.86; H, 5.17 per cent).

The acid was ketonised in the same manner and the semicarbazone was obtained, m. p. $132-36^\circ$. This on two crystallisations from methyl alcohol melted at $137-39^\circ$ and showed no depression in m. p with the semicarbazone melting at $136-38^\circ$, described before. The melting point showed a tendency to rise on repeated crystallisation as in the previous case.

Ethyl 2-Methyl-5-isopropylcycloheptanone-7-carboxylate (XVIII).—sodium (1.5 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (25 c.c.) and cooled in a freezing mixture. Ethyl oxalate (11 g.) was added. The solution was cooled to -15° and to this was added the similarly cooled methylisopropylcycloheptanone (8.4 g.) in two portions in the course of half-an-hour. The solution became yellowish and it was allowed to stand at -10° for 2 days. Next it was decomposed with ice and H_2SO_4 (dil.) and the separated oil was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The residue left on evaporation of the solvent was slowly heated in vacuum (50 mm.) after addition of boric acid (10 mg.). The temperature was raised from 130° to 170° in the course of 4 hours. Excess boric acid should not be used to avoid polymerisation. Next the temperature was raised to 195° and kept thereabout for half-an-hour and the pressure was adjusted to 30 mm. Finally it was distilled at 19 mm. when a yellow oil passed at $160-67^\circ/19$ mm., yield 8 g. On redistillation, it passed over at $163-67^\circ/19$ mm. or at $105-107^\circ/0.2$ mm. as a colorless oil, yield 7 g. (60%). Ferric chloride coloration in alcoholic solution was greenish blue. (Found: C, 69.23; H, 9.8. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 69.96; H, 10.07 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Keto-3-methyl-6-isopropylsuberate (XII).—To sodium (2.4 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) and cooled in a freezing mixture, was added a cooled mixture of menthone (15.4 g.) and ethyl oxalate (14.5 g.). The mixture was kept at 0° for 2 days when the colour of the solution became red. It was poured into ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid and the separated oil was taken up in ether. The residue after removal of the solvent was hydrolysed with a solution of KOH (28 g.) in methanol (250 c.c.) for 2 hours. Next it was diluted and the methanol removed on the steam-bath. On cooling it was extracted with ether to remove menthone, and the acidic fraction was isolated on acidification. The acidic fraction was thoroughly dried and esterified with a mixture of alcohol (35 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (5 c.c.) for 16 hours.

It was diluted with water and extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed with a relatively concentrated solution of sodium carbonate, washed with water, dried and distilled. The keto-ester passed over at $127-30^{\circ}/0.03$ mm., yield 4.9 g (14%). It gave a bluish violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 64.04; H, 9.38. $C_{14}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 65.97; H, 9.40 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Hydroxy-3-methyl-6-isopropylsuberate (XIII).—The above keto-ester (3.2 g.) was hydrogenated in acetic acid (15 c.c.) with platinum oxide catalyst (0.2 g.). The hydrogenation was complete in two hours (350 c.c.). The product was obtained at $120-22^{\circ}/0.02$ mm. in a quantitative yield. (Found: C, 63.68; H, 9.87. $C_{16}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 63.54; H, 10.0 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Chloro-3-methyl-6-isopropylsuberate (XIV).—The above hydroxy-ester (14 g.) was mixed in the cold with PCl_5 (10 g.). In the beginning there was a violet coloration which vanished after a few minutes. After two hours it was decomposed with ice and extracted with ether. Acidic impurities were removed with sodium carbonate solution. The chloro-ester was distilled when it passed over at $115-20^{\circ}/0.1$ mm., yield 6 g. There was a residue (3 g.) in the flask. The alkaline wash was acidified and the acidic product was collected and mixed with the residue from the flask and treated as described afterwards. The chloro-ester was redistilled and the middle fraction was analysed. (Found: C, 59.96; H, 9.03. $C_{16}H_{20}O_2Cl$ requires C, 59.89; H, 9.11 per cent).

Ethyl 3-Methyl-6-isopropylsuberate (XV).—The chloro-ester (6 g.) in acetic acid (50 c.c.) was refluxed with zinc dust (6 g.) for 6 hours. On working up in the usual way, the desired ester distilled at $116-20^{\circ}/0.1$ mm., yield 4.3 g. (Found: C, 67.11; H, 10.29. $C_{16}H_{26}O_2$ requires C, 67.09; H, 10.59 per cent).

3-Methyl-6-isopropylsuberic Acid (XVI).—The above ester (4.2 g.) was refluxed for 12 hours with a solution of KOH (5 g.) in methanol (25 c.c.). The free acid (2.9 g.) was finally isolated on distillation; b.p. $175-80^{\circ}/0.1$ mm. (Found: C, 62.05; H, 9.48. $C_{12}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 62.58; H, 9.63 per cent).

The *p*-bromophenacyl derivative, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $72-74^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 53.72; H, 5.03; $C_{21}H_{22}O_4Br_2$ requires C, 55.86; H, 5.17 per cent).

The residue from the distillation of the chloro-ester was refluxed with HI and red phosphorus, as described before, and a further quantity of the dibasic acid was obtained, which analysed as follows. (Found: C, 62.53; H, 9.52. $C_{12}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 62.58; H, 9.63 per cent). The *p*-bromophenacyl derivative (m.p. $72-74^{\circ}$), prepared from the above acid, showed no depression with the derivative described before.

4-Methyl-7-isopropylsuberone (XVII).—The above acid (4.8 g.) was converted into thorium salt and the latter on dry distillation afforded a distillate (2.6 g.). This on redistillation passed over at $99-102^{\circ}/12$ mm. The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual way, melted at $120-22^{\circ}$, on thrice crystallisation from methanol. (Found: C, 63.91; H, 10.32. $C_{12}H_{22}ON_3$ requires C, 63.96; H, 10.29 per cent).

This sample was repeatedly crystallised from methanol, when a small amount of crystals melting at $125-27^{\circ}$ with previous softening at 122° was isolated.

The semicarbazone (1.6 g., m. p. $120-22^{\circ}$) was decomposed with steam in presence of oxalic acid and the ketone (0.9 g.) was obtained, boiling at $100-102^{\circ}/12$ mm. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $-20^{\circ}.2$ (13.8 mg./c.c. in alcohol); n_D^{20} , 1.4590; d_4^{20} , 0.9082. (Found: C, 78.32; H, 12.11. $C_{11}H_{20}O$ requires C, 78.51; H, 11.98 per cent).

These experiments were carried out in the chemical laboratories of E. T. H., Zürich, Switzerland and the author places on record his grateful thanks to Prof. Plattner and Dr. Fürst for their kind help and encouragement and also for the laboratory facilities. Thanks are also due to the University of Calcutta for the award of a Ghosh Travelling Fellowship in Science.

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